

Appendix

Table 2 provides a summary of the codes, themes, and example quotations.

Table 2. Results of data analysis.

Theme	Sub-Theme	Code	Example Quotation
Business model challenges		Developing of impactful business model with end-customer value is problematic	"It's such a versatile and challenging setup." [P7]
Impact evaluation challenges	Challenges in defining the impact	The definition of impact is vague	"I think the discussion about what the real impact is and what is not has yet to take place." [P11]
	Challenges in measuring the real impact	Measuring real impact of the operation	"Measuring the impact is so central to us as it is what the performance bonuses are paid for. But at the same time, it's really difficult in this complex world to understand what real impact is." [P4]
		Interpretation of impact data	"The vast majority of data is in reasonably good condition and reasonably easily available to professionals. But you have to be a pro to get it, and that makes it all the more difficult." [P3]
	Challenges in reporting the impact	Achieving transparency in impact reporting is challenging	"Investments should have gone to an interesting destination, but the vast majority of it has been dissolved somewhere in the embers of corruption." [P2]
		Startup companies lack resources in impact reporting	"I understand that it is easy to request reporting from companies, but especially small companies do not have the resources for such reporting." [P11]
	Dilution of impact investing	Dilution of the term of impact investing	"Everyone who thinks they understand the term, uses it for their own presentations, which is a wrong way to do it." [P8]
Investment challenges	Financial infrastructure challenges	Major differences in financial infrastructures between developing countries and industrialized countries	"Important question is, how does that local financing structure work, i.e., financing is done with western assumptions and

western contract bases, so how does the local jurisprudence react to it?" [P1]

Time span of investments is too extensive for private investors "There is such a challenge of synchronizing the cooperation here." [P7]

Illiquidity of investments Weak liquidity of impact funds "The structure [impact funds] is complex and illiquid, and the value determination can be very questionable." [P2]

Lack of human resources Laborious due diligence process "We have these reporting and due diligence requirements, so it almost requires a full-time person from many startup companies, just for the discussion with financiers and the collection of material and reporting, etc." [P1]

Lack of human resources in startup companies "It [cooperation] requires quite an experienced person and it requires a lot of resources for it. It's difficult." [P1]

Shortage of finance Public sector organizations lack financial resources to invest in impact investing "We have cities and municipalities with deficits, there are no quick solutions from the budget." [P9]

Acquiring seed stage financing "Our real problem is finding equity financing, especially at this seed stage." [P10]

Illiquidity of startup shares reduces scalability of investments "Whenever we go to small companies, startups and so on, there comes the challenge of what we can do and to whom we can offer it." [P2]

Lack of impact funds "But the fact is that there is clearly a lack of product that would allow you to buy this idea [impact]." [P2]

Legislation challenges Financial regulation challenges Difficulty for a private investor to enter the impact investment market "This is limited as there is a very big minimum investment size and you must be a professional client. It hasn't been made very easy for a private investor yet, it's practically impossible now." [P2]

		Rigorous criteria for professional investor status	"The challenge is the very controlled status of a professional investor... If you consider how many investors you can find in this market area of ours, there are not very many of them who can use this product at all." [P2]
		Demanded size of impact fund entry	"In practice, the situation is that if I had a million euros and wanted to invest in an impact fund, I wouldn't necessarily be able to implement it." [P2]
	Jurisprudence challenges	Juridical challenges when investing in foreign companies	"It has been a big challenge that financing directly to these countries is not possible, because the local jurisprudence is not developed enough." [P1]
Market challenges	Lack of Competence	Actors lack the know-how of markets and investing	"There will be people in the so-called investor scene who don't know what investing is. Acting solely on green values, without understanding the investment process and its dynamics." [P3]
		Lack of skilled workforce	"Today we face a skills shortage. It is going to affect this industry and our entire growth in many areas." [P7]
	Non-market-based behavior	Actors do not operate according to market conditions in terms of operations and finance	"When there is a lot of funding available, there are actors who do not operate according to market conditions, in a field where they should operate according to market conditions." [P1]
		Blended finance depresses operating prerequisites of market-based companies	"Investments are provided in the form of a gift while still competing with commercial investors." [P1]
		Narrow allocation of subsidized investments limit business growth in certain sectors	"Yes, it [distortion of markets] happens a lot... It's still happening the wrong way, that it's focused on certain sectors that everyone wants to do now. For example, renewable energy. But then again, some sectors may be excluded." [P1]
	Small size of the local markets	Shortage of local startups in markets prevent growth	"We have a rather narrow field for these companies locally...our sights are more national, and we are also looking for international partnerships." [P7]

SIB challenges	Exiguity of SIB investments	Weak scalability of SIB projects	"The two biggest challenges are that you have to make investors understand that this is an investment target and get to the level where these investment decisions would be made by investment organizations and get a little closer to the real investing." [P4]
	Extensive size and complexity of SIBs	SIB projects are too broad of scale	"Those years of plans and construction of meters and other things are probably needed, but along the way, I'm sure you'd be able to learn by doing small-scale experiments." [P8]
		SIB projects are too expensive	"It's too stiff and too expensive. Because the same SIB issue can be implemented by the municipality making the same agreement with the service provider than it makes with the SIB organization." [P5]
Public actor challenges		Public and private actors pose dissimilar operating principles which impairs collaboration	"Often start-up companies, universities and researchers or people focusing on administration, speak completely different language. That it is quite a challenge to bring them together." [P7]
		Public actors lack substance competence in marketing and branding products and services	"It [Finnish public sector] lacks so many areas of expertise, such as marketing, creating a phenomenon, everything like that." [P9]
		Publicly funded organizations compete on financial resources with private companies	"We are all in the project group of the Ministry of Education and AVI. In that bureaucracy. And registered associations... compete with us for investments." [P9]
		Public procurement processes do not take impact investing accents into account	"How do the organizations in charge of purchases even know how to tender such an impact-based procurement? I'm not holding my breath for the next couple of years regarding that matter." [P10]
		Private investors consider public collaborations too risky	"Social actors are such a damn big risk at this stage." [P10]
